

Schedule of trial events

	Pre-randomization	Study period		Post-Intervention follow-up
Time point		0 months	3.5 months	12 (one year) months after
Subjects		Students from 80 schools (40 per group)	Students from 80 schools (40 per group)	Students from 80 schools (40 per group)
STUDY GROUPS				
Intervention		X	X	
Control		X	X	
PROCEDURES:				
Eligibility screen				
Assess schools for eligibility (eligibility screen)	X			
Invite schools to the recruitment meetings	X			
Informed consent	X			
Training				
Conduct training for research assistants [2 days]	X			
Conduct training for trainers [3 day]	X			
Conduct teachers' workshop (Teachers in the intervention arm) [2 days]	X			
Randomization		X		
IMPLEMENTATION - Teach the learning resources, monitoring the intervention administration		X	X	
ASSESSMENT - Critical Thinking about Health Test			X	X